

Recommended citation: Thomson, G. A. (2017). Development of a Series of Design Build Projects - Preparing Students for Industrial Placement . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 339-346). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698091.

Development of a series of design build projects - Preparing students for industrial placement

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ABSTRACT

Many modern engineering degree programmes make use of active learning often built around a variety of problem and project based learning activities. Structuring these to ensure a progression of both technical and professional competencies is key, with the emphasis often being focussed around the scientific and technical competencies to the detriment of the generic skills needed in industry.

This paper describes the creation and evolution of a series of major group projects over the first two years of Bachelors level degrees in Mechanical Engineering & Product Design aimed at developing students to a point where they are both confident enough and competent enough to undertake a year in industry at the end of their second year.

Mapping both the technical and personal qualities of a successful placement student and the typical entry competencies of our students, a series of requirements were developed and these structured into a coherent programme of project modules spanning two years.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, University-Business cooperation
Engineering Skills

Keywords: Industrial Placement, Skills, Employability, Project Based Learning

INTRODUCTION

To provide the best for engineering students, educators work hard to provide engaging and relevant programmes which are valued by both the students and the industries into which they will be recruited.

An increasingly common focus is the need for “employability” to try to ensure graduates emerge into the workplace with a holistic set of both technical and non-technical skills necessary to succeed and be readily useful to their employer. The use of industrial placements with students working in industry for a period of typically up to a year at some point during their degree is seen as a key part of this employability

strategy for many but it itself requires students to be adequately equipped to successfully take on these positions in industry.

1 CONTEXT

1.1 Engineering Curriculum Design

In spite of Universities often emphasising research to inform staff recruitment and other strategic decisions, increased competition for students, availability of programme quality information to potential students and governmental pressures have seen much more emphasis placed on the quality of teaching provision.

This has seen Universities rethink their curriculums to best achieve the desired outcomes. [1]

In particular while discrete under-pinning scientific knowledge remains core, a greater emphasis has often been placed on holistic curriculums which integrate technical knowledge with broader personal, organisational, problem solving, commercial and team skills. This is exemplified by initiatives such as “CDIO” which aim to provide broad based programmes delivering high levels of employability. [2]

1.2 Employability

Employability is a key driver in the provision of the majority of engineering degree programmes. This is not unsurprising in a vocational subject with graduates enrolling in degrees to allow them to be equipped with the necessary skills, knowledge and personal qualities required for a career within the discipline. In addition, employability metrics – eg. proportion of graduates in graduate level posts – are commonly used in programme and institution league tables and rankings.[3]

Achieving employability within engineering programmes involves creating a curriculum which covers not only the technical skills required of engineers but also builds the students’ confidence, people, team, commercial and other skills with these non-technical skills often to be found lacking particularly among engineering students. [4-9]

For engineering students, learning is typically developed through a blend of conventional lectures, tutorials, formal laboratory exercises and projects. While lectures may be seen as a resource effective way of transferring underpinning engineering knowledge, they often lack context and this can be particularly the case for the personal, social and professional skills needed of the employable graduate and as a result a more experiential project based learning approach can be seen as more desirable.

1.3 Industrial Placement

For students at many Universities in the UK and elsewhere there is an opportunity to take part in a short or long term industrial placement as part of their degree. This is designed to allow students to not only contextualise the knowledge and skills being developed at University but also to expose them to the workplace, its approaches, conditions and cultures and in so doing develop their employability ahead of returning to their studies and graduation. Placements are typically taken after two years of study. For satisfactory placement experiences for both the student and the employer it is therefore important that adequate skills, both technical and non-technical are built up ahead of the student undertaking the placement.

2 PROJECT BASED LEARNING

2.1 Focus

To try to develop a broad based engineering education, significant emphasis has been placed on project and problem based learning. See eg. [10-12]

Aston University in Birmingham, UK runs mechanical engineering and product design degrees following a CDIO approach. As with all degrees at Aston, they offer students the opportunity to undertake year long industrial placements between years 2 and 3.

Prior to adopting the CDIO approach the degrees at Aston were very traditional, with large numbers of discrete modules, generally focussed around core engineering science disciplines with little integration between modules or attention given to non-technical skills. Under the adoption of the CDIO principles a project based focus was evolved and a plan was developed to determine the contents of these to ensure students would grow as individuals, while also developing the necessary technical and non-technical skills and knowledge to enable them to undertake a successful placement.

Fig 1. Student journey through year and two projects

It was decided that the first two years of the programme would therefore feature four major project elements accounting for half the students' time and credits, the balance being more traditionally taught engineering science and mathematics classes. These projects would then hopefully impart many of the employability skills necessary for successful placement. Fig. 1 shows a top level approach to the resulting project curriculum with a theme identified for each project.

3 PROGRAMME DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Curriculum requirements

From reviewing research in the area and working with our own industrial board it became apparent that our previous programmes offered little opportunity for students to develop or practice their non-technical skills. These were entirely absent from the curriculum or existed in a theoretical and non-contextualised approach eg. a module in project management, taught purely by lecture and assessed by exam.

A range of technical and non-technical skills which might be required of a student entering an engineering placement were drawn up based on the literature, dialogue with industrialists, our own experiences and also the requirements of the relevant accrediting body. A list of some of these skills can be seen in table 1 with the intention that these could be developed through the project modules.

Table 1. List of Technical, Professional and Personal Competencies to be covered by project modules.

Technical Competency	Professional Competency	Personal Competency
Technical drawing	Commercial awareness	Self-reflection
Design methods	Engineering ethics	Self learning
Design for manufacture	Presentation skills	Time management
Analysis to support design	Project management	Leadership
Experimentation in design	Communication	Team membership
Critical review	Team working	Organisation
Component selection	Costing	Time keeping
Engineering standards	Meeting management	Accountability
Tolerancing	Documentation	Responsibility
Product specification	Legal responsibility	Confidence
Product requirements	Intellectual property	Empathy
Problem solving	Etc...	Etc...
Systems design
Etc...		
...		

3.2 Phasing

As with any educational approach it is important to introduce material to students at an appropriate phase in their development and also allow opportunities to reinforce, deepen and broaden the particularly key topics and where possible these link into non project areas of the curriculum.

In year 1 it was felt key that students focus on their technical and personal competency. Students were typically entering University directly from school and had come from a very heavily coached environment with often little consideration for the uncertainty and variability of real problems. They were also unfamiliar with group projects and working with others in a meaningful way. Professional competency was phased in more heavily at a later stage as students developed through year 2 and approached their placement at the end of the year.

3.3 Mapping

Table 2 shows the mapping of some of the key competencies with the student journey toward placement.

Table 2 : Mapping of core technical, professional and commercial competencies against the project modules.

	Year 1 Semester 1 Introduction to Engineering & Design Electric Car	Year 1 Semester 2 Scientific & Commercial Factors Wind Turbine	Year 2 Semester 1 Design for the User Medical Product	Year 2 Semester 2 Design for Industry Pneumatic Product
○ Topic Introduced				
◆ Topic Reinforced				
Technical Competency				
Technical drawing	○	◆		◆
Design methods	○	◆	◆	◆
Design for manufacture		○		◆
Analysis to support design	○	◆	◆	◆
Experimentation in design		○	◆	
Critical review			○	◆
Component selection			○	◆
Engineering standards		○		◆
Tolerancing	○	◆	◆	◆
Product specification	○	◆	◆	
Product requirements	○	◆	◆	
Problem solving	○	◆		
Systems design		○	◆	◆
CAD		○	◆	◆
Professional Competency				
Commercial awareness		○	◆	◆
Engineering ethics			○	◆
Presentation skills		○	◆	
Project management	○	◆	◆	
Communication	○	◆	◆	
Team working	○	◆	◆	
Costing		○	◆	◆
Meeting management	○	◆		
Documentation		○	◆	◆
Legal responsibility			○	◆
Intellectual property			○	◆
Personal Competency				
Self-reflection	○	◆		
Self learning	○	◆		
Time management	○	◆		
Leadership		○	◆	◆
Team membership	○	◆		
Organisation	○	◆	◆	
Time keeping	○	◆		
Accountability	○	◆		
Responsibility		○	◆	
Confidence	○	◆	◆	◆
Empathy			○	

Fig. 2 shows the core design artefacts associated with the project modules.

Year 1 Semester 1
Introduction to Engineering & Design
Electric Car

Year 1 Semester 2
Scientific & Commercial
Factors
Wind Turbine

Year 2 Semester 1
Design for the User
Medical Product

Year 2 Semester 2
Design for Industry
Pneumatic Product

Fig. 2. Artefacts produced by each of the projects in years 1 and 2.

4 REVIEW AND CONCLUSIONS

The programme is now at a stage of maturity with a number of cohorts having emerged from these projects and progressed into industrial placements and beyond into the workplace. Feedback from students emerging from placements is that these modules are key in helping them once in placements and while they can only partly provide some of the culture and learning they will experience once in work, certainly smooth the pathway.

Moreover the modules are seen as important in helping secure the placement posts which are typically competitively recruited among under-graduates from a range of programmes and Universities. Students are encouraged to take along project log books or other materials from their projects to evidence their development to the

potential employers and this has proved a key factor at converting interviews to offers.

A recent quote from a student is typical – “*at my interview I presented my log books which details all the projects I have taken part in from the CDIO modules at Aston. The company representative at the interview was very impressed with how the course focuses on projects and specifically mentioned that the skills I had gained as a result were well suited to the industry.*”

The approach is not without issues. The mapping aligns the technical, professional and personal topics to modules based on a theoretical ideal but this may then conflict with the theme of the module not always being a perfect fit for all the outcomes. Alternatively there may be resource issues with staff or workshop availability needing to be synchronised carefully.

The operation of the modules and the preparation of students for industrial placement is however one of continuous improvement and the approach and detail within the projects is continually evolving.

Nonetheless our experience has shown that, well-structured holistic modules are a key asset in help students obtain and succeed within industrial placements.

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